

WEB-BASED APPLICATION FOR N. S. RATNAM BROTHERS

Dilaksanraj, A.¹, Prasad, W. D. N.²

¹*dilaksanraj@gmail.com*

²*nilantha@sjp.ac.lk*

Background of the project

Introduction

In today's fast-changing business environment, it is extremely important to be able to respond to client needs in the most effective and timely manner. Most of the customers wish to see your business online and have instant access to your products or services. This project was to develop an online shopping website to expose the products of an organization through the web.

To develop an online shopping website, several Technologies must be studied and understood. These include multi-tiered architecture, server and client-side scripting techniques, implementation technologies such as PHP and relational databases. This was a project to develop a basic website where a consumer was provided with a shopping cart application to purchase products available. It was expected to learn the technologies for these developments activities while achieving the objective mentioned.

Overview of the existing system

N. S. Ratnam Brothers is a company in Vavuniya district which sells motor bikes, spare parts and electronic items. They did not have any web-based system to do their business activities at the moment. This organization used a manual file system to maintain their records on business operations.

System Analysis

Problem Analysis

At the time of problem analysis, there was no method for the organization to get customer inquiries, publish information, search products for the customers.

The identified issues that prevailed in the organization were as follows:

- Difficulty to manage customer and employee records
- Potential data losses
- The difficulty of manage a large amount of product information
- Human errors
- Time consumption

However, Due to the absence of a proper system they had the above operational issues (Fadzil 2017).

Requirement Analysis

Functional requirements related to the new system are:

- The system would manage product details.
- The system would manage the customer details (Id, customer name, customer address and customer contact details).
- The system would manage the manufacturer details (Id, supplier name).

Proposed system & objectives

The entire system was divided into two modules named as user module and admin module. The web site has a member login page which is used to get updates and future offers for consumers at the same login which can help the admin to perform his/her role. Multiuser login form is used to identify the user type and allow them to specific pages.

System Design

System design is the process of designing the elements of a system such as the architecture, modules and components, the different interfaces of those components and the arrangement of data that goes through that system.

User interface design

The total project of user interface was designed by using HTML, CSS and JavaScript. This responsive UI works with multiple platforms like mobile phone, Desktop, and I pad.

Figure 1: Main Interface

Data design

Database design is the process of producing a detailed data model of a database. This logical data model contains all the needed logical and physical design choices and physical storage parameters needed to generate a design in a data definition language, which can then be used to create a database.

Figure 2: ER diagram

Process design

Figure 1: Use Case diagram

System Development

System development activities

In this system development Laravel framework was used, Laravel is a free, open-source PHP web framework, created by Taylor Otwell and intended for the development of web applications following the model–view– controller (MVC) architectural pattern and based on Symfony.

Application development tools

In my system SQL database was used. It is clear what kind of data should be stored in the database. Since SQL is a relational database, the EER modelling approach is very useful to design the database schema since it maps well to the relational model and the constructs used in the ER model can easily be transformed into relational tables.

System testing and evaluation

Test & Evaluation (T&E) is the process by which a system or components are compared against requirements and specifications through testing. In my system, Functional testing was used to ensure that the specified functionality required in the system requirements works. It falls under the class of black-box testing. (Lozančić 2017)

Conclusion

In this project, an efficient way of developing a dynamic website was represented by using the power of PHP and My SQL. Still, a little limitation exists in the software.

This project helps in understanding the creation of an interactive web page and the technologies used to implement it. Data Model and Process Model were included in the design of the project. A precise knowledge was gained about how PHP is used to develop a website, how it connects to the database to access the data and how the data and web pages are modified to provide the user with a shopping cart application by building this project.

References

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